

Pollution of the river Ganga and the Ganga Action Plan : an evaluation

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A brief outline on the different aspects of the Ganga Action Plan has been made. The analysis of the water quality of the Ganga shows that in spite of enormous uses and misuses, the quality of the Ganga water is good though the turbidity and coliform concentrations are high. The nutrient loads like nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) are on the increase. But most of the studies are incomplete and suffer from limitations as various important aspects have been ignored in such analysis and the Ganga Action plan has made little impact on water quality. However, the sediment quality of the Ganga (though not studied properly) is good and the sediments are rich in beneficial microbes. The sediment load of the Ganga is very high and occasional dredging is necessary for cleaning the Ganga. The sediments can be profitably utilized for agricultural purposes. Some measures have been suggested to make the Ganga Action Plan fruitful and economically viable.

The Ganga (or the Ganges) and its tributaries flowing through U.P., Bihar and West Bengal, can be considered to be the lifeline of Northern and Eastern India. Most of the cities, villages and industries are situated on the banks of the river Ganga. However, the flow of the river water and its quality are in danger as a result of population explosion and consequent uses and misuses of the river to meet the ever increasing demands of the community. Enormous soil erosion in the entire basin region, agricultural run-off carrying fertilizers, pesticides etc., lack of education among the masses and lack of proper planning for water management are responsible for the deteriorating water quality of the river which is bound to be hazardous to the public health, aquatic life and the ecosystem in general. The Ganga has been regarded to be one of the most polluted rivers in the world and the area surrounding Kolkata on the river Hooghly is supposed to be exposed to the threat of serious ecological disaster^{1,2}. The pollution pattern in different segments is obviously different and depends on : (i) the transport of quality and quantum of waste load generated in the respective catchment area, (ii) quantum and quality of water received from different tributaries or other sources, (iii) degree of self-purification in the respective areas and the diurnal variations of the DO in the respective segments, and (iv) climatic variations like monsoon, summer etc. Naturally, a systematic planning on the monitoring of the different aspects of water management is needed keeping in view the flow characteristics, water use, pollutant disposal and the hydrological aspects of the riverine systems.

The pollutional aspects of the river Ganga were studied and efforts to monitor water quality and correlate the data

with environmental aspects had been attempted by NEERI (National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nagpur, India)^{3,4} and other agencies like Universities. NEERI has also published a valuable document embodying the results of studies on environmental aspects of the river Ganga for the last thirty years⁵. The Central Pollution Control Board had also initiated a regular water quality monitoring programme since 1979 through different agencies.

In view of national importance of the Ganga and extensive uses of the river water for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes over a stretch of 2500 km in most densely populated Gangetic basin, the river has attracted attention of a large number of workers. Different environmental and pollutional aspects of the river were studied and the results of these investigations are the subject-matter of a large numbers of publications⁵⁻¹⁵. In order to cope with the diversity of problems, an extensive Rs. 240 crore Ganga Action Plan was launched to clean the Ganga for better water management and use of multipurpose river systems in the country.

According to Choudhuri¹⁶, there are 100 towns located on the Ganga, of which 27 cities account for 84% pollution. The Ganga Action Plan conceived 54 locations where sewage could be diverted and treated. But the water quality of the river has not been significantly improved in spite of huge expenditure. An integrated approach for the development of the Ganga basin was made by the author and his coworkers⁶⁻⁹. Various aspects of the pollution of the River Ganga and their effect on the ecosystem had been studied. The results may be useful for the regulatory authorities. (i)

to assess water qualities for management and various uses and (ii) to prepare inventory for water pollution in the Ganga basin. It is expected that the works involved in the Ganga Action Plan should serve as a model for the other major and minor rivers in India.

The present communication describes a brief review of the works done by us and the difficulties associated with studies. It also outlines some suggested measures for making the Ganga Action Plan economically viable.

Water pollution

Table 1 presents some physicochemical parameters (average of at least 500 samples studied over the period 1985-1995). Parameters show considerable seasonal variations and segment variations. The results of our studies⁶ indicate that the quality of the river water expect at some points is generally good. The water is hard, slightly alkaline (capable of absorbing acid rains), BOD values are within tolerable limits though coliform levels are high. DO maintains a high value (except at some points) almost throughout the year indicating high reaeration capability of the river Ganga. The turbidity and sediment transport of the water are rather high but the water remains extremely transparent on keeping even over a long time. The presence of bacteriophages for *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Klebsiella*¹⁰, *K. pneumoniae* etc. and presence of radioactive substances together with transition metals¹¹ having bactericidal effects have been ascribed to be the reasons for the purification of

the river water. The quality of the Ganga water is definitely good in spite of its wide uses and extreme misuses. Except iron, the concentrations of other toxic elements like Cu, Zn, Mn, Cr, As, Hg are low or below detectable limits. Our results are corroborated by the results reported by the Sea Explorers Institute, Outram Ghat, Kolkata, from continuous monitoring of water quality for the last five years (1996-2001)¹⁷. However, contrary to the reports published previously¹² the transport of nutrients like N and P have been found to be very high⁶. It is known that NO_3^- ions are easily leached if not used rapidly by plants. Though NO_3^- contents have been found to be within safe limits (10 mg dm^{-3}), but the high organic nitrogen and NH_3N content (which indicates fresh pollution) pose potential danger⁶ as autotropic oxidation of NH_3 to NO_2^- , NO_3^- may reduce the DO levels in the river water endangering aquatic life.

The results also suggest that the P-level of water in the river Ganga has increased several times which means greater discharge of P to the sea. This is quite rational in view of increased use of inorganic fertilizers, polyphosphates in detergents, pesticides etc. According to the estimates of Meybeck¹⁸, the content of total dissolved phosphorus in rivers has been doubled or tripled whereas according to the Van Bennekom and Solomons¹⁹, flow of P in rivers have increased by a factor of 5 due to man's activities leading to serious pollution problem. This aspect needs careful consideration.

Table 1. Summary of water quality of the river Ganga
Period : 1985-1995, Main stations Palta and Dakshineswar
(Average values from at least 20 stations from Swarupganj to Kolkata)

[The samples are usually muddy but odourless, temperature range : $24-28^\circ$ in most cases (variations between 15 and 36° were also observed)]

A*											
Parameter	TDS	DS	Turbidity (NTU)	Total hardness	Alkalinity	Salinity	Ca	Mg			
Range	160-380	90-200	80-900	80-200	80-200	8-16	20-40	8-16			
Max	Mid. June - mid. Sept.	July-Sept.	July-mid. Sept.	Dec.-Mar.	Nov.-Jan.	Feb.-Apr.	Feb.-Apr.	Feb.-Apr.			
Min	Mar.-Apr.	Mar.-Apr.	Jan.-Mar.	July-Aug.	Jan.-Apr.	July-Oct.	June-Sept.	July-Sept.			
B*											
Parameters	pH	Conductivity (mho)	DO	BOD	COD	Cl^-	PO_4^{3-}P	Nitrite-N	Nitrate-N	Sulfate	Fe
(Range)	7.2-8.4	200-400	4.0-6.9 (in rare cases)	1.0-5.0	8.0-16.0	40.0	0.3-2.0	0.01-0.02	0.10-0.25	8-20	1.0-4.5
Max											July
Min		July-Apl.									Mar-Apl.

*All values except temperature, conductivity, turbidity and pH, are in mg l^{-1}

Total coliform 7300-82000 MPN/100 ml (min. in May and June, max. in July-Oct.).

Metals like Al, Mn, Cr, Hg, Cd, Zn, Ni are present in trace quantities or not detectable.

Table 2. Average values of chemical parameters of air-dried sediments of the river Ganga from Bandel to Diamond Harbour

Period : 1987-89

(20 Stations from the banks on sides of the river)

Parameters	pH	K ⁺ mg/g	Na ⁺ mg/g	Ca ²⁺ mg/100 g	Mg ²⁺ mg/100 g	C%	N%	P%	S% as SO ₄ ²⁻
Range	7.2– 8.6	0.20– 0.90	0.1– 0.90	0.60– 1.28	0.20– 0.38	0.35– 3.92	0.10– 1.50	0.60– 2.02	0.02– 0.30
Mean	7.8	0.30	0.37	0.93	0.30	2.35	0.64	1.20	0.13

However, some of the important aspects of pollution of the river Ganga have not been properly studied by us as well as other agencies due to difficulties and limitations. These are given below. (i) Due to peculiar hydrological characteristics of the river and the variable discharges of pollutional loads from diverse sources, the water quality of the river in each segment varies from day to day and even from hour to hour. The mean residence time of water in rivers is usually 12 days but the mean residence time of water for the river Ganga is likely to be low. Therefore, the water quality is expected to be highly variable. The data presented in most cases are based on grab samples and very much dependent on the composition of the source at a particular time and place only. However, the data of composite samples (a mixture of various grab samples drawn from the system at one sampling location but at different times) or integrated samples (a mixture of grab samples drawn from the system at different locations simultaneously) are required to have a better picture. (ii) In most cases, samples for dissolved oxygen, BOD etc. are taken at very shallow depths. At these depths, one would expect oxygen concentrations to be high due to atmospheric mixing. A better indication of potential oxygen problems would be to measure oxygen concentrations in the deeper parts of the river. Other pollutional characteristics are also dependent on depth and it is desirable to study pollution at different depths also. (iii) The correlation of data with the total water flow, velocity of water flow and depth of the river should be attempted. (iv) The quantum of load discharged from various outfalls and the time required for their effective neutralization and distribution in the river water should be taken into consideration in determining pollution characteristics. (v) Monitoring frequency should be high and monitoring should be made and classified into four types : (a) summer, (b) Monsoon, (c) post-monsoon and (d) winter, to have representative values. (vi) Proper attention should be made to assess the nutrient loads. (vii) Qualitative and quantitative estimations of trace metals and organics like DDT, aldrin, dieldrins, PCB etc. should be made. This aspect has drawn little attention upto now. (viii) The microbial changes and changes in speciations should be studied properly. This aspect is very important but little

work has been done. (ix) Attempts should be made to correlate the water pollution with atmospheric inputs, agricultural inputs, weathering, mining and other natural processes.

It is apparent that the proper correlation of the water quality of the river Ganga with different physicochemical or biological parameters have not been possible due to diverse and widely variable sources of pollution. Moreover, the discharge of pollutional load from the same sources are also widely variable due to multiplicity of factors like closure of the factories, construction of new factories with different pollutional loads, climatic and seasonal variations etc. In spite of all the limitations, it has been observed that the major sources of pollution of the river is well documented and the methods for the prevention of pollution are to some extent known.

Sediment pollution

One of the important lacuna of studying the pollution of the river Ganga is the lack of attempt to study the bottom sediments of the river and their proper utilization. Sediments can be regarded as sinks for organic and inorganic materials transported from the land. Trace metals, exchangeable ions (like Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺) and nutrients like N and P are expected to be mobilized in sediments as a result of natural process as well as man's activities. Therefore, monitoring sediment quality can give a long-term, cost-effective picture of pollution climate of water bodies^{20,21}.

Analysis of metals in sediments is easy and reliable. Moreover, it provides a temporary integrated picture of metal ion concentrations whereas the analysis of the constituents in the water column lacks precision and is less reliable^{20,21}. The analysis provides a transient glimpse of pollution conditions since the concentration of materials in the water column is profoundly affected by the dynamics of water (fresh water inflow, tidal exchange, wind driven mixing etc.).

The analysis of dried sediments^{7,9} (Table 2) of the river Ganga carried out by us shows that the nutrient budget of the sediments (N, P) are considerable and has been on the increase, i.e. enormous mobilization of organic matter P

and N. Mobilization of metal ions are also observed though no attempt was made to study the mobilization of micronutrients like B, Mo etc. The ion-exchange capability⁸ (a factor responsible for holding nutrients) of the sediments is appreciable. The concentration of K^+ is appreciable. The pH of the sediments lies between 7.4 and 8.6. The sediments can absorb acid rain and amenable to microbial activities. The C/N ratio of the sediments is usually of the order 10 : 1.

Ganga Action Plan

The main thrust of the Ganga Action Plan is (i) construction of sewage treatment plants for the purification of industrial and domestic effluents and discharge of pure water to the river, (ii) installation of electric furnaces for cremation, and (iii) construction of sanitary latrines to prevent defecation on the river banks (not properly included in the plan). However, the success of the project is doubtful as the installation of sewage treatment plants and their efficient running are too expensive for our country to bear unless proper resource generation is achieved to make them economically viable. Many of the sewage treatment plants did not give desired results.

Resource generation

Sewage treatment plants and biogas generation :

The success of the sewage treatment plants, therefore, to some extent depends on the production of biogas from the sewage and utilization of the slurry as manures for agricultural purposes. Though some costly biogas generation units were constructed but these were not economically viable. The N, P, K values of the slurries were not properly tested and the slurries (a source of organic manures) were not properly utilized.

The presence of toxic industrial pollutants and excessive surface active agents in sewage may prove detrimental to the successful production of the biogas²². Other biomass (plants and agricultural residues) may be mixed to increase the biogas generation²³. Slurry may be enriched by suitable nutrients for proper use.

Sediment pollution and its utilization

It is well known that the Ganga carries enormous amounts of dissolved and particulate matter due to soil erosion and unscientific discharge of wastes from sources manifold. The river transports 83 million tons of dissolved solids annually and the sediment transport is about 328 million tons²⁴. The particulate matter has caused heavy siltation raising the river beds but enormous mobilization of essential ingredients from the ecosystem. The siltation goes

unabated during the lean periods as the proper flushing of the river beds is not possible making the river beds swallow and current is reduced. During the monsoon, there is overflow of the river causing widespread flood and damage of crops, cattle, human lives and properties. Several hundred crores of rupees are spent annually to combat the menace of flood and drought. It is apparent that the depletion of water flow and ever increasing siltation are the causes of pollution of the river.

Analysis of sediments (Table 2) show that the sediments alone or with very little amount of fertilizer can be utilized in agronomy resulting in reduced dependence of fertilizer. The agronomic use of sediments have been reported^{25,26}. The use of the Nile sediments cause better nutrients uptake and improved physical texture of sandy soils. The Nile sediments also improved soil moisture content, organic matter level, soluble phosphate and total nitrogen level of desert sand soil. Thus the use of the Ganga sediments is likely to improve the soil condition and preserve soil texture to a great extent and make partial compensation for the cost of desiltation. The sediments of the river Ganga contains a large number of very efficient phosphate solubilizing bacteria²⁷ capable of solubilizing phosphates from soil, i.e. increase in available P from soils can be expected.

Pollutants are absorbed and desorbed by the sediments and there is a continuous change in pollutional load due to interaction between water and sediments. Occasional dredging is desirable to remove pollutants from the river ecosystem and to increase water flow and water holding capacity of the rivers. It will be definitely more important than the construction of sewage treatment plants for cleaning the river Ganga.

Pollution is an ever increasing socioeconomic problem causing environmental hazards and ecological imbalances but its control is a costly process. We lack sufficient resources and proper infrastructure. However, efficient management, proper mobilization of resources and strong determination are needed to combat the problem efficiently and effectively for which an integrated approach is needed which should include the aspects discussed above as well as other aspects, some of which are given below. (i) Afforestation programme in general and particularly along the banks of the river to reduce excessive soil erosion and transportation. (ii) Raising the embankments on both sides of the river (and using them as roads) using the sub soils. (iii) Improvement of inland water transport system using both motor driven and traditional boats. (iv) Modernization, diversification and reorientation of industrial units with effective pollution control devices. (v) Imparting environmental education to increase environmental awareness.

Suitable synthesis of high cost and low cost technology with judicious use of manpower on a contract basis may be useful for optimization of costs and making the Ganga Action Plan successful and socioeconomically viable.

Experimental details are given in our previous works⁶⁻⁹. Standard procedures were utilized for the estimation of water and soil pollution²⁸⁻³¹. The details of microbial work on phosphate solubilization are given in a previous communication²⁷. A brief summary of works done by us are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

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